

Deliverable D7

Title

Guidelines detailing recommendations and standards for force calibration of testing machines under dynamic force taking into account parasitic influences from multi-component forces and temperature effects

EMPIR Grant Agreement number

18SIB08

Project short name

ComTraForce

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Leading partner

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